

ISSN: 2278-4853. Vol 8, Spl Issue 2, April 2019.
Impact Factor: SJIF 2018 = 6.053

Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research

**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
“EMPLOYMENT SKILLS AND RURAL
TRANSFORMATION”**

11th, 12th and 13th April 2019

Organized by

Department of Commerce

**Manonmaniam Sundaranar University,
Tirunelveli-627 012, Tamil Nadu, India.**

PUBLISHED BY

www.tarj.in

Part - 1

42.	A STUDY ON GEM & JEWELLERY ENTREPRENEURS AND THEIR CONTRIBUTION TO INDIA'S ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT R.ELUMALAI, DR.M.SENTHILKUMAR	233
43.	CONSUMER PREFERENCE TOWARDS E- SHOPPING SURROUNDED BY THE INDIVIDUALS IN THOOTHUKUDI DISTRICT DR M.SIVAKUMAR, MRS ANUPRIYA	239
44.	POPULARITY OF VARIOUS SKILL DEVELOPMENT SCHEMES AMONG RURAL PEOPLE SAVIOUR .F	255
45.	PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF WATER CRISIS ANJALI VERMA, GUNJAN SINGH	263
46.	RURAL TRANSFORMATION IN INDIA: AN AREA OF THRUST JATINDER SINGH	277
47.	A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RURAL AREAS OF TIRUNELVELI C.PRIYA, DR.P.GEETHA	285
48.	WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN PRESENT SECENARIO DR.M.VAIRAVAN, MRS.S.SHAGIRABANU	293
49.	TRANSFORMATION OF RURAL ECONOMY: A CASE STUDY OF SHOLAGA TRIBES IN THE BARGUR HILLS OF ERODE DISTRICT OF TAMIL NADU SUMATHI S N DR. SHAIK MAHAMAD	297
50.	PROBLEM OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN CHENNAI CITY DR. R.DHARMA RAGINI, R.SUBITHA RANI	303
51.	ANALYSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN RURAL TRANSFORMATION SAM SANTHOSE.S, ARUNFRED. N	307
52.	WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS A STUDY OF TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT DR.C. THILAKAM , DR.S. PETER EMIL JEBAKUMAR	317
53.	EDUCATIONAL STATUS OF STUDENTS WITH VISUALLY IMPAIRED URMILA BHAINA, DR. HARAPRIYA SAMANTARAYA	325

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RURAL AREAS OF TIRUNELVELI

C.Priya

Ph.D(Commerce)Scholar,

Sadakathullah Appa College (Autonomous),

Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abhishekapatti, Tirunelveli

priya.chittibabu@gmail.com

Dr.P.Geetha

Assistant Professor of Commerce, Sadakathullah Appa College (Autonomous),

Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abhishekapatti, Tirunelveli

Abstract

Teachers play an important role in the construction, development and re-construction of the society. The teacher is the pivot on whom the entire educational structure rests and every teacher should definitely possess the potential and a distinct intention to do their duty with utmost devotion and derive satisfaction. To attract and retain good quality teachers is a great challenge to all educational institutions. Job satisfaction is the combination of emotional and psychological experience at any work. The successful running of any educational system depends mainly upon the teacher, the pupil, the curriculum, and the facilities. The teachers would get interested to teach their students effectively when they are satisfied with their jobs. Job satisfaction is one factor that will ensure class performance and productivity of schools. Job Satisfaction is the relationship between what everyone expects in accordance to what everyone achieves. This observational and interaction based study has been done with the purpose of understanding the current level of job satisfaction among primary school teachers in rural areas in Tirunelveli district and their influencing factors.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play an important role in the construction, development and re-construction of the society. They are the actual pillars of our nation who are the architects of our country's vision. NCTE has put great emphasis on educational development of teachers as only the best teachers can lead the nation and their corresponding societies towards a better and higher quality of life. The successful running of any educational system depends mainly upon the teacher, the pupil, the curriculum, and the facilities. Of these, the teacher is the most important one and is the pivot on whom the entire educational structure rests. To attract, and retain good quality teachers is a great challenge to all educational institutions. Every teacher should definitely possess the potential and a distinct intention to do their duty with utmost devotion and derive satisfaction. Job satisfaction is the combination of emotional and psychological experience at any work. Job Satisfaction is the relationship between what everyone expects in accordance to what everyone achieves. Job satisfaction is one factor that will ensure class performance and productivity of schools. The teachers would get interested to teach their students effectively when they are satisfied with their jobs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the job satisfaction levels of primary school teachers employed in rural areas in Tirunelveli district.
- To understand the level of importance shown by the primary schools to improve & develop employee satisfaction among their teachers.
- To understand & rate the teacher's view of various activities by primary schools & their effect on job satisfaction.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- This study is limited to the teachers working in Primary schools in rural areas of Tirunelveli district.
- This empirical study is based on and limits itself to 50 randomly collected samples from respondents, currently employed across various primary schools across rural areas of Tirunelveli district.
- Primary data has been collected through Direct Questionnaire.

METHODOLOGY:

- This section attempts to describe the methodology of the present study. It includes period of the study, sampling techniques, collection of data and tools of analysis of data.

4.1 Area & Place of Study Profile

- Tirunelveli is a district in the southern most part of India in the state of tamil Nadu and is the 3rd biggest rural district by area in the state. Rural population in Tirunelveli district accounts

to 276 persons per sq.km with children forming 11%. Literacy rate in the district is 85% which has raised by 7% over the last 10 years. Completion rate in primary education has increased to around 99% over that period with around 2000 primary schools accounting for around 3000 habitations. An approximate number of around 15000 teachers are currently employed in these primary schools and a steady decrease in number of teachers has been noticed in the period of the last 10 years.

Sampling Design

- The data collected are original in nature. For the collection of data, one hundred employees were selected as respondents by convenience random sampling method.

Statistical tools for analysis

- Tabulation
- Percentage
- Mean score analysis

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 5.1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

S No	Demographic Factors	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	44	44
		Female	56	56
2	Age Group	Below 20 yrs	10	10
		21-30 yrs	16	16
		31-40 yrs	60	60
		Above 40 yrs	10	10
		Above 50 yrs	4	4
3	Qualification	School Level	6	6
		Diploma Holder	18	18
		Degree Holder	54	54
		Post Graduate	16	16
		Professional	6	6
4	Income Group	Upto Rs.10000	32	32
		Rs.10000-20000	58	58
		Rs.20000-30000	6	6
		Above Rs.30000	4	4

5	Experience Level	Less than 2 yrs	18	18
		2-5 yrs	22	22
		5-7 yrs	36	36
		More than 7 yrs	24	24

Source: Computed Primary data

Table 5.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. There are 56% of female respondents and 44% of male respondents who have participated in the survey. Majority of respondents 60% are in age group of 31-40 years, 16% of respondents are between 21-30 years, 16% of respondents between 21-30 years and 10% of respondents are below 20 and above 50 years. On educational qualification, majority 54% of respondents have completed degree, 18% of respondents are diploma holders, 16% of the respondents are post graduates while 6% of respondents are professional. The above table reveals that 58% of respondents come under income group up to Rs.10000-20000, 32% of respondents are upto Rs.10000, 6% of respondents Rs.20000-30000, 4% of respondents above Rs.30000. According to this table 18% of respondents are having experience of less than 2 yrs, 22% of respondents are having experience of 2-5 yrs, 24% of respondents are having more than 7 years of experience, majority of respondents 36% of employees are having experience of 5-7 yrs.

Table 5.2: Motivational Factor

SI No.	Organizational behavior	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
a)	Teaching provides me with an opportunity to advance professionally.	6 (12)	9 (18)	2 1 (42)	9 (18)	5 (10)	5 0 (100)
b)	I get along well with my students.	5 (10)	9 (18)	9 (18)	2 4 (48)	3 (6)	5 0 (100)
c)	I am responsible for planning my daily lessons	3 (6)	2 (4)	1 3 (26)	2 4 (48)	8 (16)	5 0 (100)
d)	The work of a teacher is very pleasant	4 (8)	4 (8)	1 6 (32)	2 3 (46)	3 (6)	5 0 (100)
e)	Teaching encourages me to be creative.	8 (16)	4 (8)	9 (18)	1 6 (32)	1 3 (26)	5 0 (100)
f)	Promotion of employees	3 (6)	6 (12)	1 2 (24)	2 1 (42)	8 (16)	5 0 (100)

Source: Computed Primary data

From the above table, five point scale question have been taken for survey. Majority of respondents 42% are neutral when teachers were asked whether teaching provides them with an opportunity to advance professionally. while 18% agreed and 10% strongly agreed. In case of getting along well with their students 48% of respondents are in agreement, 18% of respondents are in neutral and 18% disagreed. Majority of respondents 48% agreed that they are responsible for planning their daily lessons, 26% of respondents are in neutral and 16% of respondents strongly agreed. Majority of respondents 60% are satisfied that they are praised in front of seniors, while 28% are neutral. 56% of the respondents are satisfied that the school provides adequate non- monetary incentives while 34% & 24% of the respondents are satisfied and highly satisfied respectively that their school promotes employees who perform well.

Table 5.3: Working Atmosphere

Sl No.	Organizational activities	Highly Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Highly Satisfied	Total
a)	My students are my biggest motivation	3 (6)	6 (12)	1 2 (24)	21 (42)	8 (16)	5 0 (100)
b)	Do you work harder than your co-teachers	3 (6)	6 (12)	1 5 (30)	1 7 (34)	9 (18)	5 0 (100)
c)	Working conditions in my school are good	6 (12)	5 (10)	1 5 (30)	1 7 (34)	7 (14)	5 0 (100)
d)	Do you try new ideas in your school	3 (6)	9 (18)	1 2 (24)	2 0 (40)	6 (12)	5 0 (100)

Source: Computed Primary data

Table 5.3 five point scale question has been taken regarding the working atmosphere of primary school teachers. Majority of respondents 42% are satisfied with their students as my biggest motivation, 24% are neutral while 16% of respondents are highly satisfied. In case of their working hard comparative to co-teachers 34% of respondents are satisfied, 30% of respondents are in neutral, 18% are highly satisfied and 12% are dissatisfied. Majority of respondents 34% are satisfied with their working conditions in school, 30% of respondents are in neutral and 10% of respondents are dissatisfied. The survey reveals 40% of respondents are satisfied that they try new ideas in their school, 24% of respondents are neutral and 18% are dissatisfied.

Table 5.4: Monetary Benefits

SNo	Monetary Benefit	Highly Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Highly Satisfied	Total
a)	I receive full recognition for successful teaching	4 (8)	5 (10)	17 (34)	15 (30)	9 (18)	50 (100)
b)	The administration in my school communicates its policies.	4 (8)	10 (20)	11 (22)	19 (38)	6 (12)	50 (100)
c)	Physical surroundings in my school are pleasant.	4 (8)	7 (14)	15 (30)	18 (36)	6 (12)	50 (100)
d)	I get cooperation from the colleagues	4 (8)	11 (22)	11 (22)	17 (34)	7 (14)	50 (100)

Source: Computed Primary data

From the above table 5.4, majority of respondents 34% are in neutral in case of full recognition received for successful teaching, 30% of respondents are satisfied and 10% of respondents are dissatisfied. In case of policy communication by respective schools a majority 38% of respondents are satisfied, 22% of respondents are neutral and 20% of respondents are dissatisfied. Majority of respondents 36% are satisfied with their school surroundings, 30% are neutral while 14% are dissatisfied. In case of cooperation from their co workers, 34% of respondents are satisfied, 22% of respondents are neutral and 22% of respondents are dissatisfied.

Suggestions

- Physical surroundings and administration policies in school should be improved in order to get job satisfaction among teachers.
- Although great emphasis has been given to full recognition & cooperation from co-workers can still be improved upon to motivate teachers. Superior's encouragement & active involvements in team discussions can still be further improved
- Satisfaction levels on motivational factor are high although promotion of employees can be taken care in order to maintain positive environment among teachers to further enhance the employee potential.

- Satisfaction levels on working conditions are high although management can look into transparency & new ideas implementation to further encourage involvement of teachers.
- Educational institutions to focus more on motivation of self involvement & superior engagements with teachers to enhance their job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

- The present study on job satisfaction in primary school teachers in rural areas of Tirunelveli district reveals that job satisfaction levels among teachers are relatively high and also shows employees are satisfied with various organizational activities by various primary schools.
- Although great emphasis has been given to teachers safety & individual development both can be improved upon to involve & motivate teachers.
- Educational Institutions activities such as rewarding achievements & praising teachers in front of colleagues can be further improved to improve employee motivation.
- Job satisfaction is one factor that will ensure school performance among teachers and students and productivity of schools. Job Satisfaction among teachers is the relationship between what everyone expects in accordance to what everyone achieves.
- Satisfaction levels on monetary benefits like good recognition and promotion to next level make teachers motivated to further excel in their teaching field.
- Satisfaction levels on working conditions are high and new ideas can be given to improve their standard of teaching.
- Institutions to focus more on motivation of self involvement & superior engagements with teachers to enhance their work potential. The successful running of any educational system depends mainly upon the teacher, the pupil, the curriculum, and the facilities

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